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Abstract Book

PP-4: Strengthening Leprosy Disease Surveillance Through a Shared Online Master Sheet at Colombo Regional Director of Health Services Area

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Background

Accurate and timely monitoring of leprosy patients at the field level is essential for effective disease control. However, maintaining up-to-date patient information and coordination between district and staff of Medical Officer of Health (MOH) areas has been a persistent challenge. To address this gap, a zero-cost, shared digital data management system was developed to streamline reporting, follow-up and visualization of leprosy cases all 18 residential MOH areas within Colombo Regional Directorate of Health Services (RDHS- Colombo).

Description of the Intervention/Initiative

A Google-based master sheet was developed to record details of individual leprosy cases across the district. The master sheet contains separate tabs for each MOH area, allowing data to be entered and viewed according to administrative boundaries. Access to each relevant sheet was shared with the respective MOH office, enabling them to view and update patient information in real time. When a patient is confirmed as having leprosy, the district team enter the basic case details and subsequent field-level activities are updated by the MOH team. Thus, the system functions as a two-way data entry and monitoring tool. Child cases are highlighted within the sheet to facilitate quick identification and focused follow-up.

Methods Used for the Evaluation

Feedback from MOH staff was obtained during routine supervisory visits. The functionality and completeness of the data were also reviewed through periodic checks of the shared sheets, assessing timeliness of entry, level of completeness and consistency between field and district level records.

Results

The introduction of the Google master sheet greatly improved coordination between district-level and MOH-level teams. Data entry became more timely and duplication of records was minimized. Field staff were able to visualize the updated list of active patients in their area, facilitating prompt action on case follow-up and contact tracing. The visual highlighting of child cases proved especially useful for identifying potential transmission clusters and prioritizing interventions.

Lessons Learnt

This simple, no-cost and user-friendly tool significantly enhanced information sharing and joint monitoring of leprosy cases. The collaborative nature of the platform encouraged better communication between district and MOH staff. The initiative demonstrates how readily available digital tools can be effectively adapted to strengthen disease surveillance and program management at the field level.